

NAVIGATING CORRIDORS: SINO-US RIVALRY IN THE PERSPECTIVE OF CPEC AND IMEC

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ABSTRACT

The culmination of the Cold War with the disintegration of the Soviet Union, and the emergence of the United States as a key player marked a significant turning point in the 20th Century. However, the rise of China challenged this unipolarity and emerged as a strategic and economic competitor to US interests in the world. This competition emanates from technical advancement, strategic alliances toward military projections, and strategic crossroads. With the depletion of land resources, oceans became the center of strategic and economic attraction for global players. In this context, the Indian Ocean, being the third largest ocean, provides immense opportunities for its littoral states and is the midpoint of worldwide trade and energy. Therefore, capturing this route or maintaining influence in the Indian Ocean Region (IOR) has become a paramount desire of great powers. The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and India-Middle East Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) are divergent projects with the ambition to counter the interests of global rivals. India, China, and the US are the key players in these two projects to serve the vested interests of the involved actors. The outset of IMEC in the presence of a Chinese-driven project (CPEC) manifests the signs of global rivalry in the IOR. Also, it depicts the global endeavors to maintain the hegemony in the IOR. The Regional Integration Theory has been employed to explore two strategic corridors with diverging interests and their implications on the IOR which unfolds how these infrastructure projects shaped economic and geopolitical power. This paper examines how India and the U.S. view CPEC as a threat to their influence, complicating support for IMEC, which was seen as a rival to China's BRI. Ultimately, these corridors reflect distinct regional priorities, contributing to ongoing geopolitical competition and global power dynamics.

Keywords: IOR, CPEC, IMEC, Global rivalry, Regional Integration Theory, Sino-US rivalry.

INTRODUCTION

The collapse of the Soviet Union altered global dynamics. It gave the US leverage to promote liberal values and democracy worldwide because

the end of the Cold War made the US the sole superpower with no ideological threat and penetration of communism (Nye, 2017). However,

in the post-Cold War period, the rise of China in the East Asia region with its authoritative culture posed strategic and ideological obstacles in promoting American-led liberal values. In addition, the growing Chinese economic strategies, like the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), challenge U.S. influence in the region. Moreover, China's emerging influence in the area in the form of the Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), a key part of the BRI, not only enhances China's access to the Arabian Sea, but reduces dependency on the Malacca Strait, and strengthens its presence in South Asia and the Indian Ocean. To counter the Chinese clout in the region, the U.S. introduced the Build Act (2018) and the India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC), aiming to counter China's influence in the Indian Ocean Region (IOR) and beyond (SHAHID et al., 2023). The Indian Ocean has drawn the attention of global players like the US due to its vast geo-economic significance and strategic position. Its key role in connecting the Western world and its proximity to critical oil and natural resource shipping routes has made it a focal point of competition. Additionally, the region's instability, particularly in the Middle East, further underscores its importance in global geopolitics. Therefore, in recent years, the geo-strategic environment of the IOR has evolved rapidly due to the increasing tensions between the United States and China (Oh, 2024). However, American policymakers are denying BRI flagship port and road projects in terms of a "string of pearls" and spreading the information in statements of a debt trap to maintain the influence of decreasing order. Apart from this rivalry, CPEC is a key initiative of China's BRI designed to improve the connectivity between China and Pakistan, initiated in 2015. CPEC is more than just an economic project; it is also a strategic effort to ensure geopolitical sway in South Asia therefore CPEC encompasses infrastructure initiatives, energy projects, and the enhancement of the Gwadar Port, also situated at the rim of the Persian Gulf, China's ambitions for worldwide economic interconnectedness (Khan et al., 2018). In addition, the US Build Act 2018 was passed to secure the financial goals of Washington's foreign policy. However, Critics of the Build Act's

effectiveness frequently focus on its inability to challenge China's BRI adequately. Experts argue that the Development Finance Corporation (DFC) has failed to focus on projects that directly challenge the BRI, enabling China to sustain its influence in developing countries (Roberts & Schaefer, 2021). Furthermore, the locus of this rivalry is multidimensional encompassing economic and military spheres, affecting important trade routes and economic corridors essential for realizing wider geopolitical interests. In the contemporary era, Chinese endeavors are remarkable to promote the infrastructural expansion of the BRI for prosperity in developing states to improve living standards and avoid conflicts (Bano & Batool, 2024).

On the contrary, the IMEC unveiled at the G20 Summit in 2023, signifies a joint initiative involving India, the United States, the European Union, and important Gulf nations. Established as a balance to China's BRI, IMEC seeks to develop an extensive trade in the IOR, the Middle East, and Europe. The corridor targets to promote economic development, improve regional stability, and lower logistical obstacles, as a strategic effort to mitigate China's increasing influence (Monroe, 2023). These corridors reflect the ongoing Sino-U.S. rivalry for global dominance, with regional players like Pakistan and Gulf states navigating this competition within the framework of regional integration because the US has lost the confidence of the capitalist class in the region due to dictate offensive policies. On the contrary, Xi's leadership accepts multilateralism or regional integration aspects for sustainable development in the form of blocs and alliances (Siddiqua, 2023).

Theoretical Framework:

This study seeks to explore the Sino-U.S. competition through the lens of regional integration theory. It will compare CPEC and IMEC, examining how regional and global interests diverge and converge in this context. Ernst B. Haas was a leading academic in international relations, especially regarding European integration after World War II. His research focused on comprehending how and why countries decide to integrate, creating supranational institutions and entities because

Europe is affected more than the rest of the world in terms of the distractions of economic, social, and political after two world wars and developed again by aligning the interests (Haas, 1970) . Regional integration theory (RIT) intends to elucidate the creation and evolution of regional global organizations. A basic definition of regional integration includes four essential components and collectively adequate characteristics: state participants, organizational capability, multilateral approach, and geographical closeness (Schimmelfennig, 2018). CPEC reflects China's commitment to energy projects that link Pakistan with China and potentially other regions like South Asia, Central Asia, and the Middle East. These projects aim to reduce trade barriers and increase economic interdependence. According to regional integration theory (RIT), financial integration lowers the risk of conflict as countries benefit from each other's prosperity. CPEC promotes RIT by strengthening economic ties, political cooperation, and social connections, to transform the region into a hub of economic and social growth (Amir, 2016) . Whereas, the IMEC presents another convincing argument favoring RIT, which emphasizes the significance of interlinking ages between countries to promote economic growth, regional stability, and social progress. This corridor enhances global trade by providing an alternative to traditional routes like the Suez Canal, which improves trade efficiency and opens new markets, linking regions with complementary economic strengths (Khan et al.,2024). The IMEC faces challenges in creating a regional trade hub due to geopolitical conflicts, funding issues, and competition with China's CPEC. India and the U.S. hesitate to invest because of strategic concerns, On the one hand, India views CPEC as a shift in regional power, while the U.S. sees it as part of China's broader geopolitical strategy. But, despite challenges like unequal advantages and debt risks, Beijing's regional integration focuses on economic partnerships. However, there are a few logistic constraints the IMEC struggles with such as infrastructure funding and land control issues, and the U.S. military presence in the Indian Ocean, being the major fault line in making this

cooperation difficult (Yaseen et al., 2024). Regional Integration Theory (RIT) suggests that deviation from key principles like cooperation, equality, and mutual benefit can lead to failure, as seen with the USSR's collapse in the Cold War period. Examples of regional integration depend upon multiple factors and the failure and success of any project or organization can be drawn from history the ASEAN and the EU demonstrate successful integration, but SAARC's projects in South Asia face delays due to dependence on great powers and lack of cohesion.

The challenges of the 21st century are significant, with global politics and rivalries among key players being major obstacles. Therefore, reliance on external influence complicates regional initiatives like the BRI, which aims to promote integration but faces resistance due to competing geopolitical interests. (Saqib & Naazer, 2023) . The main objective of applying this theory in this study is to determine whether both corridors are primarily motivated by mutual economic interests or if the IMEC is strategically aimed at countering Xi's policies, particularly about the marginalized maritime states in the Indian Ocean Region (IOR). For this purpose, the following hypothesis has been formulated.

Hypothesis:

The establishment of the IMEC regional trade hub network faces significant challenges due to strategic rivalries, as India and the United States are reluctant to engage with the project, perceiving it as a counter to their geopolitical interests, particularly about China's CPEC and the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI).

Genesis of Sino-US Rivalry:

The tensions between Beijing and Washington stem from deep historical roots, starting with events like the 1882 Chinese Exclusion Act, which reflected racial prejudice and labor competition fears in the U.S. This early discrimination was followed by ideological differences, with the U.S. promoting democracy and capitalism while China embraced communism. Over time, changing geopolitical dynamics, particularly in the Yellow River region, intensified these disparities, fostering a lasting

sense of distrust and rivalry for global influence (Lee, 2003). However, in the 1960s, the relationship between China and the Soviet Union worsened and US diplomacy exploited this division to benefit itself, resulting in a reconciliation with Beijing during the 1970s through the efforts of Kissinger (Kalinovsky & Daigle, 2014).

With the dawn of the 21st century and the dissolution of the USSR in the 20th century, China's swift economic expansion posed an economic and strategic challenge to US interests. After the 9/11 attacks, the U.S. emerged with financial and technological supremacy, while the Bush administration's offensive stance on terrorism proved economically beneficial to Chinese investors. This led to trade conflicts, concerns over intellectual property, competition for resources and markets, and differing views on democracy and human rights. These ideological differences fostered distrust between the U.S. and China, which now compete for power, particularly in the Asia-Pacific. Once seen as a dormant giant, China now plays a central role globally, challenging the U.S., which has strengthened partnerships in the region. Meanwhile, China has asserted its territorial claims in the South China Sea and expanded its military presence. Power dynamics in international relations are constantly shifting. (KISSINGER, 2010). In addition, the US has been dictating the world in the context of balancing arms and wars. At the same time, Chinese leadership has distorted the unipolarity through economic initiatives to promote regional growth on all continents of the world for prosperity, which emphasizes multilateralism through the lens of regional integration, unlike Washington to just focuses on the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) and omits the rest of the continents further tensions aroused when BRI was launched by Chinese in 2013, marking a significant change in China's foreign policy as it took an unusual step toward globalization. BRI consists of a range of infrastructure projects that are being developed and carried out in more than 130 nations. These investments consist of projects related to transportation, communication, water, and energy. BRI initiatives, like CPEC, attract numerous

developing nations in Asia and globally, anticipating that enhanced infrastructure will eventually better their challenging economic conditions (Dunford & Liu, 2019). Although the US has been maintaining a hegemon position in this ocean to contain all great powers, the dynamics of these tensions escalated when Beijing's interests were focused on the Indian Ocean maritime routes for sustainable access in regional and cross-over markets in short lines from Xinjiang to the direct NAS North Arabian Sea through soft port infrastructure. Additionally, Xi's foreign expertise challenged the Indo-Pacific command by improving its naval nuclear capabilities as a third strike from the sea and trade giant after the results of Washington's nuclear alliances with IOR key players such as Australia, the United Kingdom, and the United States signed a pact intended to discourage China by strengthening of Australia's military strength, especially via the procurement of nuclear-powered submarines and QUAD Quadrilateral Security Dialogue, which includes Australia, Japan, India, and the United States, to deter Beijing (Zarrar & Gichki, 2022).

CPEC vs. IMEC: A Comparative Analysis:

Global commerce has been viewed as a cornerstone of compensation since ancient eras. The exchange of goods and services over long distances via sea and other methods has been prevalent worldwide, even in the absence of monetary or financial systems. To enhance trade and commercial interactions between them, states utilize various strategies and tools that can ease and broaden their economic relationships.

In today's world, the establishment of economic corridors is seen as crucial for promoting trade, enhancing economic ties, and enhancing regional integration. Therefore, the geopolitical landscape in South Asia is fundamentally unstable due to the alteration of world powers' policies regarding this region, which increases uncertainty. CPEC serves as a structure for regional connectivity even though it will bring advantages not only to China and Pakistan but will also positively influence Iran, Afghanistan, the Central Asian Republic, and the surrounding region (Bhat, 2018). The improvement of geographical connections,

featuring upgraded road, rail, and air transport systems with regular and open exchanges of growth and personal interactions, fosters understanding through academic, cultural, and regional knowledge and traditions. The increased flow of trade and business, alongside the production and transportation of energy for more efficient enterprises, coupled with enhanced cooperation through a win-win approach, will create a well-connected, integrated region marked by a shared destiny, harmony, and development. The CPEC represents a move towards economic regionalization within the globalized context. It established tranquility, progress, and a mutually beneficial approach for everyone involved (Qazi, 2020).

From a strategic viewpoint, the corridor will bring unlimited benefits to China, as after completion, it will expand the number of trade routes between China and other regional countries. China imports 60 percent of its oil from the Middle East, and 80 percent of that is transported to China through the long, expensive, and dangerous piracy-rife maritime Malacca Strait route through South China, East China, and the Yellow Seas. At present, transportation of energy through the Strait of Malacca takes around 45 days, which could be easily abridged to less than 10 days if done via Gwadar port as it provides the best possible land and sea routes for this purpose. Thus, the Gwadar-Xingjian route can serve as an alternative to the Malacca Straits for energy transportation, which will be time- and cost-effective. It will also enable China to import energy and find new markets for its products in Central Asia, Africa, and the Middle East (Ghaffar & Khan, 2024).

On the other hand, IMEC's bold trade and investment plan includes an eastern corridor that connects India with the UAE, Saudi Arabia, Jordan, and Israel, along with a northern corridor that links those Middle Eastern nations to Europe. IMEC will enhance existing road and maritime transport routes to boost connectivity and economic integration between Asia and Europe through energy infrastructure, railways, high-speed cables, and shipping lanes. The nations involved in IMEC account for 40% of the global population and approximately 50% of the world economy further Passage will depend on the

seaports, roads, and logistics centers of the UAE and Saudi Arabia, enhancing the significance of these Gulf Arab nations as vital points in international trade networks. Examining this corridor necessitates taking into account the rivalry among major powers in the so-called “new Cold War” between the Sino-U.S. leaderships. The concept of the United States collaborating with other technologically advanced nations to successfully challenge the BRI through alternative routes and regional mini-lateral frameworks is not a recent one (Hansen, 2024). Consequently, due to varying geopolitical interests and views on multipolarity, each nation along IMEC’s route will uniquely perceive this transcontinental corridor while Washington will perceive IMEC as a way to curb China’s economic ascendance in the Middle East and strengthen ties between Gulf Corporation Countries states and the West, whereas officials in Abu Dhabi and Riyadh will see this trade route as a way to enhance their connections in Europe and North America alongside those with China and other nations from the East and Global South. From the viewpoints of UAE and KSA, the leading global forces—the US, China, and Russia—are not the only ones influencing the geopolitical and economic equilibrium of the world. “Middle powers” like the Emirati and Saudis are similarly impacting the global order (SURI et al., 2024). Whereas the I2U2 Group was established in 2021 by the US, Israel, the UAE, and India, this coalition intends to improve collaboration in various areas such as energy, water, food security, transportation, health, and space, utilizing private sector investment IMEC focus to expand upon the I2U2 Group and chase a significantly bolder array of goals but unrest in region creating a notion of failure in context of Indian investors lack of attention (Hameed, 2024).

The tensions existing between India and China influence specific geopolitical dynamics related to IMEC and New Delhi's motivations to engage in this transcontinental corridor. As Chinese-Indian relations hit a low due to their border disagreement, these two Asian powers are vying for influence, with New Delhi striving to counter China’s dominance in nations throughout the Himalayas and South Asia. India's conflicts with

Pakistan are also significant. India has consistently opposed the BRI, largely because the CPEC passes through land controlled by Pakistan that New Delhi claims as its sovereign territory. Consequently, New Delhi views this corridor as a chance to gain increased economic influence over Beijing and Islamabad by participating in a natural substitute for the BRI (Ali, 2023).

The security and growth for all in the region (SAGAR) is crucial for comprehending the strategic dynamics of the IOR, particularly in light of the geopolitical competition between Chinese and Americans due to the stance of the Indian Navy as a net security provider whereas IMEC also kind of objective under the SAGAR. Historically, Pakistan has largely exercised a veto on overland connectivity linking India and the

West. According to an Indian foreign policy expert, IMEC is determined to bypass this Pakistani veto, paving the way for greater economic integration between India and Europe through the Middle East without engaging with Islamabad as long as Indo-Pak territorial issues are unresolved. However, IMEC is facing a lot of challenges in terms of financial frameworks and the Levant crisis which has delved into new security concerns for Arab States (Vinodan & Kurian, 2024). But to some extent, both the corridors signify distinct but related approaches within the larger Sino-U.S. competition. CPEC highlights China's goal to redefine international trade paths in its favor, whereas IMEC represents a united effort to establish a more equitable and robust global economic framework.

Table: 1

Founder	China & Pakistan (CPEC)	USA & India (IMEC)
Partners	China and Pakistan, with minimal cooperation from regional states such as KSA	India, USA, UAE, Saudi Arabia, European Union.
Policy Objectives	“Win-Win” Energy Security, access to NAS North Arabian Sea via Gawadar Port, promotion of regionalism, and reduction of dependency on the Malacca Strait. People's interaction in various sectors	The purpose to develop alternatives to chokepoints like the Malacca Strait. Broaden international trade pathways and enhance economic ties. Multilateralism environment.
Investment Scale	Pakistan's initial funding is \$62 billion (BRI allocation), and it is dependent on budget excesses and postponements.	Valued in the hundreds of billions, dependent on participant dedication and political agreement in the memorandum.
Financial & Institutional Framework	Exim Bank of China, China Development Bank, and ICBC. JCC-PD&SI and VC/NDRC	-
Ecological Issues	Infrastructure developments create environmental issues in delicate regions.	Aims to rely on sustainability via renewable energy and low-emission initiatives.
Phases	Second / 2.0	-
Futuristic aspects	Prolonged regional integration, yet susceptible to geopolitical and security issues.	Will be Relying on robust political determination and steady financial support.

Source: Adapted by researcher

Divergence and Convergence of Interests:

Zero-sum factors are prevalent in international relations, and the competing and complementary interests in the Sino-US competition over CPEC

and IMEC highlight the complexities involved because strategic corridors are not just infrastructure projects but also areas where the current geopolitical landscape is changing. Meanwhile, rivalry highlights the nature of great power politics, and the economic overlaps highlight the interdependencies in a globalized world. However, from Beijing policy advisors, CPEC goes beyond mere economic benefits; it embodies a vision of a multipolar world where greater influence can be asserted, contesting U.S.-led systems. Therefore, Washington plans to counteract China's growth by promoting IMEC, encouraging alliances through Delhi engagement, and presenting a connectivity vision that aligns with its geopolitical interests (Bongiovanni, 2024). At the same time, this competition also highlights the constraints of one-sided strategies, as both countries acknowledge the interlinked character of contemporary economies and the opportunities for shared advantages in strategic partnerships. As for Pakistan, CPEC has offered hopes of economic growth and infrastructure development while also triggering worries about debt reliance and sovereignty issues, as the possibility of CPEC enhancing economic and military collaboration between China and Pakistan adds complexity to the geopolitical dynamics in the region, especially concerning India (Hanjra et al., 2025).

On the contrary, India's engagement in IMEC signifies its strategic partnership with the U.S. while also showcasing its increasing ambitions to take a key role in influencing regional trade and connectivity. For Middle Eastern nations, IMEC presents a chance to diversify their economies away from oil while simultaneously acting as a geopolitical counterbalance between two significant powers and even initiating warfare at the regional level due to the absence of regional key members. The U.S. perceives IMEC as a means to counter China's influence in worldwide infrastructure funding, especially along trade paths linking Asia to the West via the Indian Ocean, in terms that might conflict with the wider, global trade ambitions of the U.S. and Europe, which prioritize smooth intercontinental trade pathways instead of local benefits (Rizzi, 2024). As India enhances its maritime infrastructure to bolster these trade routes, it is likely to encounter

heightened tensions with China, particularly in areas such as the Strait of Hormuz, where a large share of the world's oil shipments transit, whereas New Delhi collaborates with the U.S.; it is wary of completely coordinating its policies with Washington's strategic interests, favoring a flexible approach in its foreign policy in the sense of insecure energy security if Houthi's or any non-state actors deter the supply chain of India from the Red Sea. Concerns over naval conflicts arising from both projects underscore the contradiction of regional unity via strategic corridors (Hamzah & Seniwati, 2025). On one side, these initiatives seek to close gaps, improve connections, and unify areas into cohesive economic structures; conversely, they intensify current maritime conflicts as regional countries compete for dominance over key ports and maritime routes that support the economic feasibility of the corridors.

Regional Integration through Strategic Corridors:

Corridor's strategic rivalry underscores that infrastructure is not merely a pathway for goods and services; it serves as a significant tool for shaping global economic frameworks and synchronizing political objectives. China's viewpoint is that CPEC represents a strategic investment aimed at enhancing a wider economic and geopolitical framework expansion towards the Middle East and North Africa region (MENA), while IMEC aims to improve the trade connections between India and Europe via the Middle East, providing an alternative to routes controlled by China. RIT offers to expand cooperation in the conflicted region to connect states for mutual benefits through the interdependence of economies to avoid escalations at regional proximities (Khan R. A., 2024). However, in South Asia, Washington's policy is divergent from European convergence because, in this region, American foreign experts enhanced conflict through military assistance for the containment of communism as a result of four nuclear weapons, of which two were anti-American, such as China and Russia; further, two were ideological opponents of each other Pakistan and India states aroused at close geographies

contrary to socio-economic is at worst level in both rivals of south Asia; hence, Chinese has the ambition to unite this region after achieving the successful execution model of CPEC to integrate India as a trade partner at regional level for the prosperity of developing economies. While in Iran, close to CPEC, the Chinese and Indians are pursuing their energy interests without any confrontation. Furthermore, the Middle East, due to its strategically important waterways, continues to be a focal point for naval rivalry. Both the United States and China have bolstered their naval presence in the area, with the U.S. upholding a considerable military footprint because of its interest in protecting the energy resource supply lines. As IMEC progresses, rivalry for dominance over these sea paths may result in increased naval tensions, even though IMEC fundamentally depends on the stability of key chokepoints like the Bab el-Mandeb Strait and the Suez Canal, which are already military zones because of their geopolitical significance. The success of the corridor relies on regional powers' capability to guarantee safe transit for goods and services across these waters (Hussain & Naqvi, 2024).

Nevertheless, Iran and Central Asian states are emerging in this vision to secure geo-economic interests. On the other hand, infrastructure projects under the CPEC plan connect Sino-Pak-Iran underdeveloped western areas with global markets, which makes this initiative correspond with both countries' domestic goals of addressing regional economic inequalities and promoting stability in Xinjiang and Balochistan, provinces that are characterized by ethnic tensions and strategic importance because local stakeholders emphasize gaining regional economic advantages, including job creation, integration within the area, and enhancement of infrastructure, then shift for outer autonomy (Hussain et al., 2024). The strategic rivalry between the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and the India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) highlights how infrastructure projects in the Indian Ocean region serve as tools of geopolitical influence, not just trade facilitation. CPEC, a key part of China's Belt and Road Initiative, deepens Pakistan's ties with China, shifting it away from its historical alignment with the U.S., while IMEC

was constructed to counter China's dominance by providing an alternative trade route between India, the Middle East, and Europe. This rivalry is further intensified by military competition, as both the U.S. and China enhance their naval presence in the region, competing for control of critical maritime chokepoints like the Bab el-Mandeb Strait and the Suez Canal. The success of both corridors depends on regional stability, but the growing militarization poses a significant challenge to peaceful development.

Conclusion:

This study concluded that the rivalry between the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and the India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) can be analyzed through regional integration theory, which argues that infrastructure projects play a crucial role in shaping both economic and geopolitical power. This study investigated two divergent projects led by two competitors with variations of interests manifested that India views CPEC as a Chinese-led initiative that threatens its regional dominance, while the U.S. sees it as a challenge to its strategic interests, especially as China's influence expands through its Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). Resultantly, these geopolitical concerns make it difficult for India and the U.S. to support or invest in alternative projects like IMEC, which could be seen as a rival to CPEC and BRI. Moreover, this study also highlighted how these corridors, backed by China and the U.S., reflect distinct regional priorities and contribute to the shifting global power balance. Multilateral frameworks such as the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) and Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) aim to ease tensions, but the rivalry between these corridors illustrates the challenge of balancing economic cooperation with geopolitical competition. Ultimately, the region remains a critical battleground for strategic influence, as both economic integration and geopolitical interests continue to shape the future of global power.

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